

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LOAN WORDS IN HAUSA AND YORÙBÁ LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This paper is a comparative study of borrowed words in both Hausa and Yorùbá Languages. Nigeria is a multi-lingual nation, having many languages. Out of these numerous languages, three were recognized as regional languages, they are Hausa, Igbo and Yoruba. But we have regional Languages that are regarded as official languages of the regions, this is how we have Hausa, Igbo and Yorùbá as indigenous languages. This paper works on how Hausa and Yoruba borrowed words from different languages around them. It discusses the various ways the two languages borrow, and from the languages the loan words are from. The adaptability of the borrowed words into the languages were discussed. The theory used for this work is optimality because it is a theory of general model of how grammars are structured and a model of the organization of natural human language sound system. It established that borrowing is not alien in the world languages. At the end, we established that no language is an Island of its own, this makes the two languages in question to borrow words to enrich their vocabulary and add to their lexicon. The various words borrowed were itemized in different ways and for different purposes. The findings shows that both languages have loan words as a result of typological patterns and other interaction between the two languages and the languages they borrowed words from.*

Keywords: *Comparative analysis, loan words, Hausa, Yoruba, Optimality.*

Introduction

Language is essentially a medium of communication, it is a universal human phenomenon. We communicate our ideas, thoughts, emotions and signs with it. All these may not be possessed by a language, it has to borrow from other languages that come in contact with it. Such borrowed items helped in enriching, expanding and developing the language. Relationships between languages have existed for many years. This linguistic borrowing can be attributed to immigration, commerce, Religion and trade as people were exposed to a wide range of ethnolinguistic environments. Through these interactions, people were exposed to various linguistic contexts, words, and phrases were borrowed to accommodate these encounters Yorùbá and Hausa cases are no exception, the two languages influence each other despite the fact that they are not from the same language family. Hausa

is from Afro-Asiatic while Yoruba is from Niger-Congo family. The two languages borrowed from each other and from other languages.

Yorùbá loaned words from English language which expanded its vocabulary over time. There were also instances of the two languages that borrowed from each other. Anderson et al (1973) observes that when cultures come into contact with one another, borrowing takes place primarily in the realm of lexical item. This is also corroborated by Newman, O. (1996) when he says Hausa belongs to the Chadic language family, itself a constituent part of the Afroasiatic phylum. Hausa is said to belong to the chadic group of Afro-Asiatic Language family to which Arabic also belongs (El Wafiy, 2005 in Danzaki 2015). It is spoken widely in West Africa and some parts of Central Africa. Dawud (2001:4) considered it to be the third most important indigenous language in Africa after Arabic and Swahili. Lexically, Hausa has borrowed

words from other languages it has contact with but most of its loanwords have come from Arabic and English of the language of colonial masters.

Oden, C (2016) opines that Language borrows freely from one another; usually, this happens when some new object or institution is developed for which the borrowing language has no word of its own. For example the large number of words denoting as the world language are from Italian. This is to say no language is an Island of its own. Lexical borrowing is a common phenomena as it is one of the consequences of linguistic contact. Virtually, every language has enriched its vocabulary by borrowing from others. Written records of lexical borrowing make it clear that 15th century English is quite noticeably different from 21st century English. English Language borrows from so many languages which earn it its popularity and wider usage in the whole world. It borrows from French, Persian, German, Hindi, Sanskrit, Spanish, Japanese, Chinese, Dravidian, American Indian Language, Arabic and even from African languages. As it is applicable to the foreign languages, so it is for Hausa and Yorùbá. A large part of the vocabulary of the Yorùbá language are loaned words from other languages particularly from English, Hausa and Arabic; also, Hausa language borrows from Yoruba, Arabic, English and from the language that exist at their border end. World most influential languages also borrowed some words from other languages they had contact with. For instance, English has borrowed extensively from French language, French borrowed from Latin and Arabic while Arabic which is considered as a donor language also borrowed words from Paris and Roman languages to express or name things that were new to them. (Muhammad S.I. 1978). The words being borrowed were structured to align with the phonology of the recipient language. For instance, when Hausa borrowed words from any language, it writes or pronounces it in accordance with Hausa phone/phoneme by substituting the sounds that are not in the language with those ones they have, which are closely related.

This borrowing is due to language contact in a heterogeneous society as observed by Olaoye (1997). Also, Kòmọláfẹ (2014) corroborates it when he says, the words borrowed are however made to conform to the morphological and phonological structure of the borrowing language.

This is what Awóbùlúyì (1994) notes that the effects of borrowing now make Yorùbá to feature the voiceless bilabial plosive /p/ as in pépà 'paper'; pẹ̀nsùrù, 'pencil,' the occurrence of high vowel initial words (e.g. álọ̀mù 'alum') consonant sound cluster and consonant ending word. (Oníbrẹ̀d "bread seller" which are now known in Yorùbá.

Borrowing into Yorùbá as into any other languages is through auditory and graphological perception (Owolabi 1989). Awóbùlúyì (2008) opines that it is more advantageous to borrow words into Yorùbá from English. His reason for that is pre-eminent roles of English in Nigeria as the language for every official matters. Awóbùlúyì (2016) states that the words were borrowed with both meaning and graphology pronunciation which is referred to as lexical words in all the languages. Meaning is what the word stands for in orthography, and pronunciation is how it sounds. This observation makes him to conclude that, some words are borrowed in these three ways: borrowing the meaning alone, borrowing the orthography/phonology and borrowing the two together.

A study investigates how Hausa, a West Chadic language (Afro- Asiatic family) remodels loanwords from English (Indonesian-European) to suit its pre-existing phonology. Loanword adaptation is quite inevitable due to the fact that languages of the world differ from one another in many ways, phonologically, syntactically, morphologically and so on (Inkelan 2011, 2003). Based on this claim, receptor languages therefore employ ways to phonologise new words borrowed into their vocabulary to fit and to conform to native structure demands.

Research Questions

This research work is guided by the following questions:

1. Do the Hausa and Yorùbá originate from the same family?
2. Do the Hausa and Yorùbá have the same number of speech sounds (consonants and vowels)?
3. Do the Hausa and Yorùbá borrowed from the same languages or different Languages?
4. Do the Hausa and Yorùbá acculturate the loaned words in the same way?
5. Do the Hausa and borrowed from the same number languages?

Statement of the Problem

Hausa and Yorùbá are two indigenous languages spoken in Nigeria and in other countries of the world. As the languages are in Nigeria, this paper wants to investigate their relationship regarding the family lineage/of where the two languages belong to in the world, whether they are Island of their own or they borrow/loan words from other languages of the world. To establish how the two languages acculturate the borrowed words to conform with the rules of their languages and the languages they borrowed from; Also to explain how the loan words have undergone phonological or structural changes. The phonological changes are how these languages replace the non existence of certain consonant phonemes in the borrowed words in Hausa and Yorùbá.

Method used for Data Collection

The writers have adopted optimality approach. Oral interview forms the basis of data collection through lecturers and students. Secondary source was also adopted, where many writings, books, journals and dictionary were perused and samples from these sources were adopted. Through these, we were able to deduce how the two languages adopted their borrowed words.

Theoretical Framework

Optimality theory is a theory of a general model of how grammar are structured. It is introduced in the early 1990 as an alternative model of the organization of natural human language sound system by the linguist, Alan Prince. The theory is applicable to different subfields of linguistics like phonology, morphology and syntax. It borrows fundamental aspect from Generative Grammar (G.G). Optimality theory also involves the roles of consonants and various other functions as one of the most important pillars. Optimality Theory (OT) relies on an input-output mapping architecture. Provisionally, the input to optimization in syntax can be assumed to consist of predicate-argument structure, function features and lexical items since it relies on a unique type of constraints to regulate the input-output mapping, makes it to be an appropriate theory to apply to loan words.

OT models grammar as systems that

provide mappings from inputs to outputs: typically, the inputs are conceived of as underlying representation, and the outputs as their surface realizations. It is an approach within the larger framework of G.G. It is originated in a talk given by Alan Prince and Paul Smolensky in 1991 which was later developed by the same authors in 1993. It was later expanded by Prince & John J. McCarthy. OT supposes that there are no language-specific restrictions on the input, this is called richness of the base. Every grammar can handle every possible input. For example, [a language] [without] complex clusters differ on how they will [resolve] [this] [problem;] some will epenthesis e.g. [Falasak], or [Falasak], if all codas are banned and some will delete e.g. [fas], [fak], [las], [lak], candidates, however much they deviate from the input. This is called freedom of analysis. The above explanations and examples reveal that optimality theory is appropriate for this research. These are the methods to be applied to the borrowed/loaned words in the languages to make it conform with the rule of grammar of the host language.

Hausa and Yoruba Compared

Hausa and Yorùbá stemmed out of different language family. Hausa is said to belong to the chadic group of Afro-Asiatic language family to which Arabic also belongs Ei-wafiy (2005 & Dawud (2001). And it is spoken widely in West Africa and some parts of Central Africa.

Elugbe (2011) traces the origin of Hausa when he stated that the area postulated as the Afroasiatic homeland is the Ethiopian highlands on area in which most of the branches of Afroasiatic are represented. It is an area of extreme diversity in which some languages remain isolated they have not been classified because they are small and distant. From this area, the Chadic people (Hausa, Margi, Higi, Mandara, Tera etc), first moved into the Chad and Chard basin and from there westwards. They now inhabit Niger, Northern Nigeria, Chad and Northern Cameroon.

Yoruba on the other hand sprung out of Niger-Congo family as portrayed by Elugbe (2011). The Niger-Congo Languages from the largest group in Africa. All the Languages of Southern Nigeria (including most of the middle belt) indeed of most of West Africa, as well as most of central and Southern Africa are Niger-Congo.

From this, one needs to be convinced that the two languages are not from the same family, though they are indigenous languages in Nigeria, and partially, they are regarded as the official language in their different regions. Hausa is an Afroasiatic languages related to Arabic, Hebrew, Berber, Amharic and Somali among other languages. Working on the loan/borrowed words, one cannot do away with speech sounds, it is the speech sounds of one language that each language borrowed into

their own, this makes us to investigate into the speech concerning sounds of Hausa and Yorùbá (i.e. consonants and vowels) Hausa has thirty-four (34) consonants in standard Hausa, and thirteen (13) vowels comprising five (5) short vowels, five (5) long vowels and (3 to 4) diphthongs, (Sani, M.A.Z. 2005). Yorùbá Language on the other hand, has eighteen (18) consonants and twelve (12) vowels comprising seven (7) oral vowels and five (5) nasal vowels, Ow9lqbi (1989) & Qláwúwo

Table 1: Hausa Consonants

(a)

/b/	/B/	/m/	/f/	/fy/	/t/	/d/	/d/	/l/	/r/	/n/	/ŋ/	/ɲ/	/S/	
/Z/	/ts/	/r/	/sh/	/c/	/j/	/y/	/g/	/w/	/h/	/r/	/,/	/ky/	/y/	/ky/
/kw/	/kw/	/gy/	/gw/	/‘y/										

Source: M.A.Z. Sani (2005)

Twenty-six (26) out of these consonants are known as simple consonants:

(b)

/b/	/d/	/m/	/f/	/t/	/d/	/d/	/l/	/r/	/n/	/ŋ/	/n/	/s/	/z/	/ts/	/r/	/sh/	/c/
/j/	/y/	/k/	/g/	/w/	/h/	/r/											

Source: M.A.Z. Sani (2005)

The other eight (8) are called consonants with secondary articulation. They are:

/fy/	/ky/	/ky/	/kw/	/kw/	/gy/	/gw/	/‘y/
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Source: M.A.Z. Sani (2005)

Table of Yorùbá Consonants

Yorùbá consonants are divided into two, oral consonants and nasal consonals. Sixteen (16) oral consonants and two (2) nasal consonant making eighteen (18) together in Yorùbá.

Oral Consonant

a

/b/	/d/	/f/	/g/	/gb/	/h/	/j/	/k/	/l/	/m/	/n/	/p/	/r/	/s/	/x/	/t/	/w/	/y/.
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Sources: Owolabi (1989) & lówúwo (2018)

Nasal consonants

b	/m/ and /n/.
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Source: Owolabi (1989) & lawwo (2018)

Table II

Table of Hausa Vowels (a)

Short vowel	a i o u e
Long	aa /ii/ oo/ uu / ee
Diphthong	ai / au / iu / ui

Table of Yorb Vowels (b)

Oral	a e . i o . u
Nasal	an . n in . n un

Source: Owolabi (1989) & lawwo (2018)

TONES

The two languages are tonal. Hausa is a tonal language likewise Yorb. Hausa has three tones likewise Yorb its counterpart. These tones are extremely important in distinguishing meaning and grammatical categories in the two languages. The Hausa tones are high, low and falling and that of Yorb are high, low and mid tone. In Hausa, short and long vowels show difference in meaning in some cases. The three (3) diphthongs are /ai/, /au/ and /ui/ are high, low and mid respectively as portrayed in this table.

Table of the Tones with their Mark

Tones in Hausa

There are three (3) basic tone patterns in Hausa.

Table III (a)

High	(/)
Low	(\)
Falling	()

Source: M.A.Z. Sani (2005)

Tones in Yorb (b)

High	(/)
Low	(\)
Mid	()

Source: Owolabi (1989) & lawwo (2018)

From the table, high tone of Hausa is unmarked while the unmarked tone of Yorb is mid on words. High and low are marked in Yorb and mid tone do not exist in Hausa language at all.

Table of Borrowed Words into the Languages

Arabic to Hausa

Table IV

(a)

Arabic	Hausa	Gloss
Ad-dunyah	duniya	World
Al-basil	Albasa	Onion
Al-Miqas	Almakashi	Scissors
Mu'alimun	Malami	Teacher
Madrasatun	Makaranta	School
Al-maut	Mutuwa	Death
Al-akhira	Lahira	Heaven
Waqtu	Lokaci	Time
Al-imam	Liman	Spiritual leader
Siyasa	Siyasa	Politics
Kharaj	Haraji	Tax
Al-qalam	Alkalami	Pen
Harfun	Harafi	Consonant

Source: Literary work & Oral interview

English to Hausa

(b)

English	Hausa	Gloss
Principal	Frinsifal	Principal
Table	Taburi	Table
Register	Rijista	Register
Secretary	Sakatare	Secretary
Certificate	Satifiket	Certificate
Commissioner	Kwamishina	Commissioner
Church	Coci	Church
Report	Rahoto	Report
Premier	Firimiya	Premier
College	Kwaleji	College
Telephone	Tarho	Telephone
Manager	Manaja	Manager
Soldier	Soja	Soldier
Barrack	Bariki	Barrack

Source: Literary work & the Interview

Fulfulde to Hausa

(c)

Fulfulde	Hausa	Gloss
Kawu	Kawu	Uncle
Nagge	Nagge	Cow
Bukkaro	Bukka	Hut
Kindirmu	Kindirmo	Yoghurt
Mura	Mura	Cold

Source: Literary work & the Interview

Kanuri to Hausa

(d)

Kanuri	Hausa	Gloss
Zango	Zango	Camping place
Maako	Mako	Week
Kasugu	Kasuwa	Market
Yarima	Yarima	Prince
Cirooma	Ciroma	Chieftancy title

Source: Literary work & the Interview

Yoruba to Hausa

(e)

Yoruba	Hausa	Gloss
Ìsáná	Ashana	Matches
Akòwé	Akawu	Secretary
Agogo	Agogo	Clock
Gèlè	Gyale	Veil
Pákí	Kwaki	Cassava
Dírèba	Direba	Driver
Páànù	Kwano	Iron Sheet
Ḳèkè	Keke	Bicycle
Mótò	Mota	Motor

Source: Literary work & Oral Interview

Tables of Borrowed Words into Yorùbá

Loanwords from Arabic to Yorùbá

Table V

(a)

Arabic	Yorùbá	Gloss
Ad-du'a	Àdùrà	Prayer
Al-barakah	Àlùbàríkà	Blessing
Ar-ra'd	Ààrá	Thunder
Zaman	Sámọ́ón	Sky, heaven
Sabab	Sábàbí	Cause, reason
Fakhr	Fáàrí	Decent/decency
Shar'ah	Şèríà	Judgment
Tifl	Túfùlù	Baby, child.
Waqt	Wákàtí	Time, hour.
Taqah	Táakà	Power, force, ability.
Al-marad	Àmọ́dì	Disease.

Source: Literary work & Oral Interview

English to Yorùbá.

(b)

English	Yoruba	Gloss
Rubber	ṛóbà	Rubber
Church	Şọ̀òsì	Church
Court	Kọ̀òtù	Court
Bread	Bùrédì	Bread
Frame	Féremù	Frame
Office	Ófìsì	Office
Alum	álọ̀mù	Alum

Source: Literary work & Oral Interview

Loanwords from Hausa to Yorùbá

(d)

Hausa	Yorùbá	Gloss
Albasa	Àlùbòsà	Onion
Amma	Àmọ́	But
Suna	Súná	Naming
Gero	Jéro	Millet
Dawa	Dáwà	Guineacorn
Anfani	Ànfàní	Usefulness
Tawwada	Tàdáà	Ink
Bunsuru	Mèsóró	Goat
Kananfari	Kànáfùrù	Alum
'yarciki	Èsìkì	A kind of gown won by men

Source: Literary work & Oral interview

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 (a) and (b) reflect the consonant sounds of the two languages. From the table, we can see that the number of consonant sounds of Hausa out-numbered that of Yorùbá. Hausa has thirty-four (34) while Yorùbá has only eighteen (18). This thirty-four consonant sounds are in standard Hausa, but twenty-six (26) out of these consonants are known as simple consonants while the remaining eight (8) are called consonants with secondary articulation. Yorùbá consonants in (b) on the other hand is divided into two (2), namely oral and nasal consonants as reflected in the table. This shows that the number of consonants to be changed while borrowing into Hausa Language may be more than that of Yorùbá.

Table II (a) and (b) speak about the vowel sounds of the two Languages. Hausa has five (5) pairs of single vowels in standard Hausa of which five are (5) short and five (5) are long vowels known as monophthongs, the two vowels are in the table above. In standard Hausa, there are two different diphthongs 'ai' and /'au/' but /'ui/' and /'iu/' may also be considered in some aspect. Yorùbá has twelve (12) vowels which are divided into seven (7) oral and five (5) nasal respectively. But the seven (7) are usually reiterated by the scholars because it is among the speech sounds (i.e. the alphabets). We regarded the nasal vowels as separate because it is not the combination of 'a' and 'n'. it is pronounced in the word as one.

Table III (a) and (b) are reflection of tones in the two Languages. Tone can be described as a pitch of voice on which each syllable of a word is uttered naturally so as to convey a proper meanings of the word... (Sani M.A.Z 2005). Every syllable has its tone in Hausa; some are uttered on a high tone (pitch) and other on a low tone (pitch). There are two (2) basic tone patterns in Hausa, high, low and falling tones as shown in the table above. This is also buttressed by Amfani (2010) when he declares that Hausa is a tonal language and both tones and vowel length play crucial roles in distinguishing the meaning of words. As a tonal language, it has two (2) basic tones i.e. (high, low) and falling tone.

Hausa and Yorùbá, the most widely spoken indigenous languages in Nigeria borrowed words from Arabic and English to enrich their vocabularies. Not only that, they also borrowed from other indigenous languages they have contact with. The borrowings continue as new discoveries emerge.

Table IV, a, b, c, d and e are a display of the samples of the words borrowed from five different languages into Hausa.

Iva: shows some words borrowed from Arabic to Hausa language.

IVb: Itemized some English loanwords in Hausa language

IVc: This is the Fulfulde loanwords displayed here, and in

IVd: shows the samples of Kanuri loanwords into Hausa language.

IVe: shows the borrowed words from Yorùbá to Hausa, the two languages that are being compared.

Table V is a display of loanwords in Yorùbá language.

Table V a shows the array of Arabic loanwords in Yoruba language.

Table V b is Hausa loanwords in Yorùbá and

Table V c shows the English loanwords in Yoruba language.

The situation of Yorùbá is also the same with Hausa where the language borrowed more words from English and Arabic languages than in any of the Nigerian languages. Infact, all the names of the week in Hausa as well as all words denoting the fundamentals of Islam are of Arabic origin. It is worthy to note that there are more laonwords from Arabic and English to Hausa language than from any of the indigenous languages in Nigeria.

But there are situations where high and low tones come together on a given syllable, given rise to what is known as falling tones. However, words in Hausa are not tone marked in the orthography. It is only noticed during through the pronunciation.

Yorùbá on the other hand has three tones as shown in the table, High, low and mid. These tones are marked on the vowels and on the nasal consonants (m&n) if the function as a syllable in a word. It is observed that tones performed two outstanding functions of lexical and grammatical in Hausa Language. This assertion is also interested by Ugwu & Ugwu, 2015) when they opines that Hausa language employs tone to mark grammatical forms. Yoruba tones performs lexical and semantics function.

Table iv (1-v) reflects the borrowed/loaned words from five different languages to Hausa. It borrowed from Arabic, Fulfulde, Kanurl, English and Yorùbá. There used to be deletion, replacement and addition of speech sounds from the loaned words to make it conforms with the

speech sounds of Hausa. The consonants sounds of the borrowed word that is not in the Hausa Language will be replaced with the one in the ones that the speech sounds are the same or similar. Pertaining to the vowel sounds, it is also done by dropping or replacement or atimes exchange of vowel sounds to conform with the rules of host language. For example the following consonant (p,q) does not exist in Hausa language which are found in the borrowed Language Hausa will replace it with these, F,K,. Also these vowels (e, o) does not exist in Hausa, but exist in Yorùbá These vowels will be used to replace it e, o All these is to buttress what (Newman (1996) says when he observed that lexically Hausa has borrowed extensively from other languages.

Table (v) (I-II) shows the loanwords from /DESS/COE/ILORIN/Arabic English and Hausa to Yorùbá. All these language do not have the same alphabets i.e. speech sounds, some are differ. A situation where the word to be borrowed has the speech sounds that Yorùbá do not have, it will be replaced with the ones that have the same sound or the ones that the place or manner of articulation is similar to make it conforms with the rules of Yorùbá replaces the speech sound of the borrowed word from English and other languages that have such sounds:

C,Q is replaced with K.

Ph, V are replaced with F

Ch are replaced with Š

X_i are replaced with S

In Yorùbá language there is no consonant cluster or consonant ending a word. If these type of words are loaned into Yorùbá, vowels will be used between the consonant clusters. And the case of word that consonant ends. The vowel may be added or the ending consonant may be dropped. There are two categories of loanwords in Yorùbá.

From the analysis, one will be convinced that in comparing the loanwords of the two languages Hausa has more consonants sound than Yorùbá likewise vowel sounds. Also, Hausa loaned words from many languages than Yoruba. The vocabulary of Hausa is enlarged than that of Yorùbá.

Conclusion

This paper delved into the comparism of how Hausa and Yorùbá borrowed words into their

languages in order to increase their vocabularies. The paper spelt out origin of the languages from the language family we then did a sort of introduction by examining the views of scholars on the languages and the contribution of those that worked on loanwords. The work presented the speech sounds in terms of the consonant sounds, vowel sounds and the tone because the languages are tonal, though there is no accent put on Hausa. Then it went to deduce the words that are borrowed from different languages and how they conform with the rules of the two languages. From the analysis, it was revealed that Hausa is a language that borrow from many languages than Yorùbá while Yoruba borrowed from three languages in its vicinity. Conclusively, no language is an Island of its own, they borrow from each one another to accommodate new developments in their languages and to enrich their vocabularies.

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APPENDIX

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e=c

ė=2

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